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Review Article

Harnessing Nature's Power: Antidiabetic Medicinal Plants

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ABSTRACT

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by hyperglycemia due to inadequate insulin production or ineffective insulin use. Despite the availability of pharmacological treatments, managing diabetes without adverse effects remains challenging. Current therapies, including insulin and oral antidiabetic agents, are often associated with significant side effects, necessitating the exploration of alternative approaches. In recent years, medicinal plants have garnered increasing attention as potential therapeutic agents for diabetes management. Traditional systems of medicine, such as Ayurveda, continue to play a crucial role in healthcare, particularly in developing countries, where plant-based treatments are culturally accepted and widely used. This review explores various plant species with documented antidiabetic properties, focusing on their ability to regulate glucose levels, enhance insulin secretion, or inhibit carbohydrate metabolism. Compounds such as glycosides, alkaloids, flavonoids, and terpenoids have demonstrated potential in reducing hyperglycemia and associated complications. By investigating plant-based remedies, we aim to provide an alternative, complementary approach to diabetes management, emphasizing the importance of ethnobotanical research in discovering new, safer treatments for this global health challenge.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a group of metabolic disorders with one common manifestation -hyperglycemia (1, 2). Diabetes mellitus, being a multifactorial disease, demands multiple therapeutic approaches. Global studies on diabetes mellitus have reiterated that primary prevention is necessary and drastic steps must be taken to diagnose the disease early

on, provide effective management and also take steps to prevent the onset of disease in high-risk subjects. According to WHO, plant-based traditional system of medicine is still the mainstay of about 75– 80% of the world population, mainly in the developing countries, for primary healthcare because of better cultural acceptability, better compatibility with the human body and lesser side

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effects (3) . According to the fifth edition of the World Diabetes Atlas released by the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), as of 2011, the total adult population in the age group of 20-79 years stands at 4.3 billion, out of which 366 million live with diabetes, which is set to increase to 552 million by 2030 (4). Ayurveda is an ancient system of medicine originating in India, and is an extension of yoga. Its two most famous treatises, Charak Samhita and Sushruta provide evidence of a rich tradition of herbal medicine in India. Historical and anthropological studies have repeatedly demonstrated the importance of yoga's 'upanishadic' roots and philosophical basis. In India, there is a high degree of reliance on and cultural acceptability of Ayurveda medicine in favour of traditional systems of medicine. The rural population in India is heavily dependent on traditional medical systems (5). In an earlier study, we found that 67.7% of patients with diabetes attending our outpatient department used CAM, in particular naturopathy (6). Currently available therapies for diabetes include insulin and various oral antidiabetic agents such as sulfonylureas, biguanides, α -glucosidase inhibitors, and glinides, which are used as monotherapy or in combination to achieve better glycemic regulation. Many of these oral antidiabetic agents have a number of serious adverse effects; thus, managing diabetes without any side effects is still a challenge (7). An estimated 143 million people suffer from diabetes worldwide and the number is growing rapidly (8). Recently, some medicinal plants have been reported to be useful in diabetes worldwide and have been used empirically in antidiabetic and antihyperlipidemic remedies. Antihyperglycemic activity of the plants is mainly due to their ability to restore the function of pancreatic tissues by causing an increase in insulin output or inhibit the intestinal absorption of glucose or to the facilitation of metabolites in insulin dependent processes. More than 400 plant species having

hypoglycemic activity have been available in literature, however, searching for new antidiabetic drugs from natural plants is still attractive because they contain substances which demonstrate alternative and safe effects on diabetes mellitus. Most of plants contain glycosides, alkaloids, terpenoids, flavonoids, carotenoids, etc., that are frequently implicated as having antidiabetic effect (9). The severity of damage triggered by hyperglycemia on the respective organ systems may be related to how long the disease has been present and how well it has been controlled. Several symptoms such as thirst, polyuria, blurring of vision, and weight loss also accompany diabetes (10).

Classification of Diabetes Mellitus

Type 1: Associated with absolute insulin deficiency

A. Immune-mediated

B. Idiopathic

Type 2: Adult-onset, Associated with insulin resistance

Type 3:

A. Genetic defects of β -cell function

B. Genetic defects in insulin action

C. Diseases of exocrine pancreas

D. Endocrinopathies

E. Drug-or chemical-induced

F. Infections

G. Uncommon forms of immune-mediated diabetes

H. Other genetic syndromes sometimes associated with diabetes

Type 4: Gestational diabetes mellitus (11)

Management of diabetics :

Effectively managed through lifestyle modifications such as

1. Weight loss,
2. Balanced diet,
3. Regular exercise.

When these interventions are insufficient to control blood sugar levels, medications or insulin therapy may be recommended (12).

Medicinal Plants as an Alternative Source of Antidiabetic Agents

Natural products, particularly of plant origin, are the main quarry for discovering promising lead candidates and play an imperative role in the upcoming drug development programs [13-15]. Ease of availability, low cost, and least side effects make plant-based preparations the main key player of all available therapies, especially in rural areas. For centuries, many plants have been considered a fundamental source of potent antidiabetic drugs. In developing countries, particularly, medicinal plants are used to treat diabetes to overcome the burden of the cost of conventional medicines to the population [16]. Nowadays, treatments of diseases including diabetes using medicinal plants are recommended [17] because these plants contain various phytoconstituents such as flavonoids, terpenoids, saponins, carotenoids, alkaloids, and glycosides, which may possess antidiabetic activities [18]. The antihyperglycemic effects resulting from treatment with plants are usually attributed to their ability to improve the performance of pancreatic tissue, which is done by increasing insulin secretions or by reducing the intestinal absorption of glucose [16]. Herbal

medicines and plant components with insignificant toxicity and no side effects are notable therapeutic options for the treatment of diabetes around the world [19].

Herb-Drug interactions in diabetes:

The co-administration of antidiabetic herbs and pharmaceutical agents may result in HDIs leading to enhanced effects (which may be desirable clinically), decreased pharmacological effects, or adverse drug events, such as hypoglycaemia [20].

Conventional antidiabetic drugs

Low levels (or absence) of insulin leads to type 1 diabetes, and administration of insulin is indicated for treatment of this condition. Type 2 diabetes, the most common type of diabetes, is caused by insulin resistance; conventional pharmaceutical medications against type 2 diabetes include: i) sensitizers that increase the sensitivity of target organs to insulin, ii) secretagogues that increase the level of insulin secreted from the pancreas, and iii) α -glycosidase inhibitors (e.g., acarbose) that reduce the gastrointestinal absorption of glucose. The sensitizers include biguanides (e.g., metformin) and thiazolidinediones (e.g., pioglitazone), while the secretagogues include sulfonylureas (e.g., glibenclamide, glimepiride, gliclazide, tolbutamide) and meglitinides (e.g., repaglinide). [21].

Genus	Species	Geographic Zone	Activity	Reference
<i>Acacia</i>	<i>Acacia catechu</i>	Nepal, India	antihyperglycemic	[22]
	<i>Acacia modesta</i>	India and Pakistan	antihyperglycemic	[23]
	<i>Acacia arabica</i>	India	hypoglycemic and antihyperglycemic	[24]
<i>Acalypha</i>	<i>Acalypha indica</i>	India	antidiabetic	[25]
	<i>Acalypha langiana</i>		antidiabetic	[26]
<i>Achillea</i>	<i>Achillea millefolium</i>	India	antidiabetic	[27]
	<i>Allium sativum</i>	India (Ayurveda), Indonesia, Iran, Cuba, Mauritius, Togo, China (TCM)	α -amylase inhibitor, hypoglycemic, α -glucosidase inhibitor, antihyperglycemic	[28,29]
<i>Aloe</i>	<i>Aloe ferox</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[30]

	<i>Aloe vera</i>	India (Ayurveda), Ghana, Mauritius, Uganda, Tanzania, Traditional Chinese medicines, Trinidad and Tobago, Iran, Pakistan, Philippines, Saudi Arabia	α -amylase inhibitor, hypoglycemic	[31-33]
<i>Alpinia</i>	<i>Alpinia calcarata</i>	India, Sri Lanka	antidiabetic	[34,35]
	<i>Alpinia galanga</i>	India	antidiabetic	[36]
	<i>Artemisia parviflora</i>	India	antidiabetic	[37]
	<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i>	India (Ayurveda), Mauritius	hypoglycemic, α -amylase inhibitor	[38-40]
<i>Berberis</i>	<i>Berberis aristata</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[41]
	<i>Berberis asiatica</i>	India	antidiabetic	[42]
<i>Brassica</i>	<i>Brassica juncea</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[43]
	<i>Brassica oleracea</i>		antihyperglycemic	[44]
	<i>Brassica rapa</i>	India	antidiabetic	[45]
<i>Buddleja</i>	<i>Buddleja asiatica</i>	India	antidiabetic	[46]
<i>Butea</i>	<i>Butea monosperma</i>	India	antidiabetic	[27]
	<i>Butea frondosa</i>	India	antidiabetic	[47]
<i>Caesalpinia</i>	<i>Caesalpinia bonducella</i>	India	α -amylase inhibitor	[48]
<i>Calamus</i>	<i>Calamus tenuis</i>	India	antidiabetic	[49]
	<i>Calamus erectus</i>	India	Antidiabetic	[50]
	<i>Calotropis procera</i>		Antidiabetic	[51]
<i>Capparis</i>	<i>Capparis aphylla</i>		antihyperglycemic	[52]
	<i>Capparis decidua</i>	India, Pakistan	Antidiabetic	[53]
	<i>Capparis sepiaria</i>	India	Antidiabetic	[54]
	<i>Capparis spinosa</i>	India (Ayurveda and Unani)	Antidiabetic	[55]
<i>Caralluma</i>	<i>Carallumaadscendens</i>	India	Antidiabetic	[56]
	<i>Carallumaumbellata</i>	India	antihyperglycemic	[57]
<i>Carissa</i>	<i>Carissa carandas</i>	India (Ayurveda, Unani, and Homoeopathy)	Antidiabetic	[58]
<i>Cassia</i>	<i>Cassia auriculata</i>	India, Tanzania	Antidiabetic	[59]
	<i>Cassia fistula</i>	India	Antidiabetic	[60]

	<i>Cinnamomum cassia</i>	India (Unani, Ayurveda) Japan, China, South Africa	antidiabetic	[61]
	<i>Cinnamomum impressinervium</i>	India	antidiabetic	[62]
	<i>Cinnamomum tamala</i>	India (Ayurveda)	hypoglycemic	[63]
	<i>Cinnamomum verum</i>	India (Ayurveda)	α -amylase inhibitor	[28]
	<i>Cinnamomum zeylanicum</i>		α -glucosidase	[64]
	<i>Citrus sinensis</i>	India	antidiabetic	[65]
<i>Clerodendrum</i>	<i>Clerodendrum glandulosum</i>	India	antidiabetic	[66]
	<i>Clerodendrum colebrookianum</i>	India	antidiabetic	[46]
	<i>Clerodendrum infortunatum</i>	India	antidiabetic	[67]
	<i>Clerodendrum phlomidis</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[68]
<i>Coccinia</i>	<i>Coccinia cordifolia</i>	India	antidiabetic	[69]
	<i>Coccinia grandis</i>	India (Ayurveda), Sri Lanka	antihyperglycemic, α -glucosidase inhibitor, α -amylase inhibitor	[28,70-72]
	<i>Coccinia indica</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[43,63]
<i>Costus</i>	<i>Costus igneus</i>	India	antidiabetic	[73]
	<i>Costus pictus</i>	India	antidiabetic	[74]
	<i>Croton klotzschianus</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[75]
	<i>Croton zambesicus</i>		antidiabetic	[76]
<i>Cucumis</i>	<i>Cucumis callosus</i>	India	antidiabetic	[77]
	<i>Curculigo orchiooides</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[78]
<i>Curcuma</i>	<i>Curcuma angustifolia</i>	India	antidiabetic	[79]
	<i>Curcuma domestica</i>	India	antidiabetic	[27]
	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	China, Bangladesh, India (Ayurveda), Indonesia, Laos	antidiabetic	[33,80]
<i>Cuscuta</i>	<i>Cuscuta reflexa</i>	India, Bangladesh	antidiabetic	[49,81]
	<i>Cuscuta chinensis</i>	China	antidiabetic	[82]
	<i>Cuscuta americana</i>	Trinidad and Tobago	antidiabetic	[83]
<i>Cyperus</i>	<i>Cyperus kyllinga</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[84]
	<i>Cyperus laevigatus</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[85]

	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[86]
	<i>Delonixelata</i>		antidiabetic	[87]
<i>Desmodium</i>	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i>	India (Ayurveda), Sri Lanka	antidiabetic	[70,88]
	<i>Dioscorea opposita</i>	China, India (Ayurveda), China (TCM)	antidiabetic	[33,80,89]
	<i>Diospyros melanoxylon</i>	India, Sri Lanka	antidiabetic	[90]
	<i>Diospyros peregrina</i>	India	antidiabetic	[91]
<i>Elephantopus</i>	<i>Elephantopus scaber</i>	India	antidiabetic	[92]
	<i>Elephantopus mollis</i>		antidiabetic	[93]
<i>Embelia</i>	<i>Embelia madagascariensis</i>		hypoglycemic	[94]
	<i>Embeliaribes</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[95]
<i>Enicostema</i>	<i>Enicostema axillare</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[96]
	<i>Enicostema littorae</i>		antidiabetic	[97]
<i>Erythrina</i>	<i>Erythrina indica</i>	India	antidiabetic	[98]
	<i>Erythrina variegate</i>	India	antidiabetic	[87]
<i>Eugenia</i>	<i>Eugenia jambolana</i>	India (Ayurveda)	α -amylase inhibitor	[83,99]
	<i>Eugenia polyantha</i>	India, Indonesia	antidiabetic	[100,101]
<i>Euphorbia</i>	<i>Euphorbia caducifolia</i>	India	antidiabetic	[102]
	<i>Euphorbia dioeca</i>		α -glucosidase inhibitor	[103]
	<i>Euphorbia drumondii</i>	India (Ayurveda)	hyperglycemic	[104]
	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i>	India, Bangladesh, Nepal	α -glucosidase	[105-107]
	<i>Euphorbia ligularia</i>	India	antidiabetic	[62]
	<i>Euphorbia neriifolia</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[108]
	<i>Euphorbia prostrata</i>		antihyperglycemic	[109]
<i>Ferula</i>	<i>Ferula aassa-foetida</i>	India (Ayurveda), Iran, Afghanistan	antidiabetic	[110,111]
<i>Ficus</i>	<i>Ficus amplissima</i>	India (Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani)	antidiabetic	[112]
	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i>	India (Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani)	antidiabetic	[101, 113]

		homoeopathy), Southeast Asia		
	<i>Ficus carica</i>	India (Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani, homoeopathy)	antidiabetic	[114, 115]
	<i>Ficus cunia</i>	India	α -glucosidase inhibitor	[116]
	<i>Ficus glomerata</i>	India (Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani, homoeopathy)	antidiabetic	[63,117]
	<i>Ficus palmata</i>		antidiabetic	[118]
	<i>Ficus racemosa</i>	India (Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani, homoeopathy), Bangladesh, Southeast Asia	antihyperglycemic, hypoglycemic, α - glucosidase and α - amylase inhibitor	[119,120]
	<i>Ficus religiosa</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[113]
	<i>Ficus virens</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[121]
<i>Glycyrrhiza</i>	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	China, India	antidiabetic	[33,122]
	<i>Glycyrrhiza uralensis</i>	India	antidiabetic	[123]
<i>Grewia</i>	<i>Grewia asiatica</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[124]
	<i>Grewia hirsuta</i>	India	antidiabetic	[125]
	<i>Grewia nervosa</i>		antidiabetic	[126]
<i>Helicteres</i>	<i>Helicteresisora</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[127]
<i>Holarrhena</i>	<i>Holarrhenaantidyserica</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[128]
<i>Hydnocarpus</i>	<i>Hydnocarpusalpina</i>		hypoglycemic	[129]
	<i>Hydnocarpuswightiana</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[130]
<i>Leucas</i>	<i>Leucas aspera</i>	India, Bangladesh	antidiabetic	[36,131]
	<i>Leucas cephalotes</i>	India (Ayurveda), Nepal, Pakistan	antidiabetic	[132]
	<i>Luffa echinata</i>	India	Antidiabetic	[64]
<i>Mangifera</i>	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	India (Ayurveda), Nigeria	α -amylase inhibitor, antihyperglycemic	[28,133]
	<i>Melia dubia</i>	India	antidiabetic	[134]
	<i>Melia orientalis</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[135]
<i>Mentha</i>	<i>Mentha arvensis</i>	India	antidiabetic	[136]
	<i>Mentha longifolia</i>	India	antidiabetic	[27]

<i>Mimusops</i>	<i>Mimusopselengi</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[137]
	<i>Momordica charantia</i>	Philippines, Vietnam, Mauritius, Trinidad and Tobago, India (Ayurveda), Nigeria, Bangladesh, Taiwan, central America	α -amylase inhibitor, hypoglycemic, antihyperglycemic	[138-141]
<i>Moringa</i>	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	South Africa, Kenya, Mexico, India (Ayurveda), Nigeria, Mauritius, Senegal	hypoglycemic	[63,142-45]
<i>Morus</i>	<i>Morus alba</i>	Iran, Philippines, Trinidad and Tobago, India (Ayurveda), China (TCM), Pakistan, Korea, Chile	antidiabetic, hypoglycemic, α -glucosidase and α -amylase inhibition	[146-154]
<i>Mucuna</i>	<i>Mucuna gigantea</i>	India	antidiabetic	[155]
	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i>	India (Ayurveda)	Antidiabetic	[43]
<i>Murraya</i>	<i>Murrayakoenigii</i>	India (Ayurveda)	α amylase inhibitor, hypoglycemic effects, antihyperglycemic	[156]
	<i>Musa Sapientum</i>	India	antihyperglycemic	[109,157]
<i>Nymphaea</i>	<i>Nymphaea nouchali</i>	Bangladesh, India (Ayurveda)	Antidiabetic	[106]
	<i>Nymphaea stellata</i>	India (Ayurveda)	α -glucosidase inhibitor, hypoglycemic, antihyperglycemic	[158, 159]
<i>Ocimum</i>	<i>Ocimum sanctum</i>	India (Ayurveda), China, Bangladesh	hypoglycemic	[160,161]
	<i>Ocimumtenuiflorum</i>	India (Ayurveda)	α -amylase inhibitor, hypoglycemic, antihyperglycemic	[28,162]
<i>Oxalis</i>	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i>	India	Antidiabetic	[27]
	<i>Oxalis griffithii</i>	India	Antidiabetic	[49]
<i>Paederia</i>	<i>Paederiafoetida</i>	China, Vietnam, India Japan	Antidiabetic	[162]
	<i>Paederia scandens</i>	China, Vietnam, India, Japan	Antidiabetic	[162]
<i>pandanus</i>	<i>Pandanus fascicularis</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antihyperglycemic	[163]
	<i>Pandanus tectorius</i>		Antidiabetic	[164]
<i>Phyllanthus</i>	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i>	Vietnam, India (Ayurveda, Siddha,	α -glucosidase inhibitor,	[114,165]

		Unani and homeopathy), Nigeria, Malaysia	hypoglycemic, α -amylase inhibitor	
	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	Thailand, Southeast Asia, India (Ayurveda)	Antidiabetic	[117,166,167]
	<i>Phyllanthus gardnerianus</i>	India	Antidiabetic	[168]
	<i>phyllanthusvirgatus</i>		α -amylase inhibitor	[169]
	<i>Phyllanthus watsonii</i>		Antidiabetic	[170]
<i>Physalis</i>	<i>Physalis angulata</i>	India	Antidiabetic	[171]
	<i>Physalis minima</i>	India	Antidiabetic	[36]
	<i>Physalis peruviana</i>	India	Antidiabetic	[172]
<i>Piper</i>	<i>Piper longum</i>	Bangladesh, India (Ayurveda)	antihyperglycemic	[173-175]
	<i>Piper nigrum</i>		α -amylase inhibitor, hypoglycemic	[28,176]
<i>Plantago</i>	<i>Plantago ovata</i>	India	Antidiabetic	[99]
<i>Plumeria</i>	<i>Plumeria rubra</i>	India	α -amylase and α -glucosidase inhibitor	[177]
<i>Polygonum</i>	<i>Polygonum hydropiper</i>	India	antidiabetic	[46]
<i>Pterocarpus</i>	<i>Pterocarpus santalinus</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[178]
	<i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i>	India	antidiabetic	[179]
	<i>Pterocarpus soyauxii</i>		antidiabetic	[180]
<i>Prunus</i>	<i>Prunus persica</i>	India	antidiabetic	[181]
<i>Rheum</i>	<i>Rheum emodi</i>	India (Ayurveda), China	antidiabetic	[182]
	<i>Rhus hirta</i>		antidiabetic	[183]
	<i>Rhus mysorensis</i>		antidiabetic	[184]
<i>Salacia</i>	<i>Salacia chinensis</i>	India (Ayurveda, Unani), Japan, Korea	hypoglycemic, antihyperglycaemic	[185, 186]
	<i>Salacia oblonga</i>	India (Ayurveda, Unani), Japan, Korea	hypoglycemic	[186,187]
	<i>Salacia prinoides</i>	India (Ayurveda), Sri Lanka, Southeast Asia	antidiabetic	[186]
	<i>Salacia reticulata</i>	India (Ayurveda, Unani), Japan, Korea, Sri Lanka	hypoglycemic, α -glucosidase inhibitor	[185,187,188,189]

<i>Sida</i>	<i>Sida acuta</i>	India	antidiabetic	[190]
	<i>Sida cordifolia</i>	Bangladesh, India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[191,192]
	<i>Sidarhombifolia</i>		antidiabetic	[193]
<i>Solanum</i>	<i>Solanum indicum</i>	Uganda, India	antidiabetic	[62,194]
	<i>Solanum trilobatum</i>	India (Ayurveda, Siddha)	antidiabetic	[195]
	<i>Solanum tuberosum</i>		antidiabetic	[196]
	<i>Solanum viarum</i>	India	antidiabetic	[49]
<i>Stereospermum</i>	<i>Stereospermum suaveolens</i>	India	Antidiabetic	[197]
<i>Swertia</i>	<i>Swertia chirayita</i>	India (Ayurveda)	Hypoglycemic	[63,198]
	<i>Swertia cordata</i>		Antidiabetic	[199]
	<i>Swertia longifolia</i>		α -amylase inhibitor	[200]
<i>Syzygium</i>	<i>Syzygium densiflorum</i>	India	Antidiabetic	[201]
	<i>Syzygium cumini</i>	Bangladesh, India (Ayurveda), Brazil	α -glucosidase and α -amylase inhibitor, antihyperglycemic	[30,49,120,202,203]
	<i>Syzygium densiflorum</i>	India	antidiabetic	[201]
	<i>Syzygium jambolanum</i>	India (Ayurveda)	hypoglycemic	[204,205]
	<i>Tabernaemontana divaricata</i>	India	antidiabetic	[62]
	<i>Tabernaemontana heptaneura</i>		antidiabetic	[206]
<i>Taxus</i>	<i>Taxus baccata</i>	India	antidiabetic	[27]
	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>	Bangladesh, India (Ayurveda)	α -amylase inhibitor, antihyperglycemic	[87,207]
	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i>	Bangladesh, Vietnam, India (Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani), Sri Lanka, Southeast Asia	antidiabetic	[106,208,209]
	<i>Terminalia catappa</i>		antidiabetic	[210]
	<i>Terminalia chebula</i>	Thailand, India (Ayurveda),	α -amylase inhibitor	[28,166,211,212]

		Bangladesh, Iran		
<i>Trichosanthes</i>	<i>Trichosanthes cucumerina</i>	India (Ayurveda)	hypoglycemic	[62]
	<i>Trichosanthes dioica</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[213]
	<i>Vaccinium vitis</i>		antidiabetic	[214]
<i>Withania</i>	<i>Withania coagulans</i>	India (Ayurveda), Pakistan	antihyperglycemic	[215,216]
z	<i>Withania somnifera</i>	India (Ayurveda)	hypoglycemic	[100,217]
<i>Zanthoxylum</i>	<i>Zanthoxylum alatum</i>		antidiabetic	[218]
	<i>Zanthoxylum armatum</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[60]
	<i>Zanthoxylum humile</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[219]
<i>Zingiber</i>	<i>Zingiber officinale</i>	India (Ayurveda), Latin America Africa	α -amylase inhibitor, hypoglycemic	[28,63,220,221]
	<i>Ziziphus nummularia</i>	India	antidiabetic	[102]
	<i>Ziziphus xylopyrus</i>	India (Ayurveda), Pakistan, China	antidiabetic	[222]

Plant Name	Country/Region	Activity	Reference
<i>Abrus precatorius</i>	India (Ayurveda, Unani, Siddha)	antidiabetic	[223]
<i>Acorus calamus</i>	India, Indonesia, America	α -glucosidase inhibitor	[105,224]
<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	India (Ayurveda)	α -amylase inhibitor	[28]
<i>Adiantum capillus-veneris</i>	India	antidiabetic	[27]
<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i>	India	antidiabetic	[225]
<i>Alangium salvifolium</i>	India (Ayurveda)	hypoglycemic	[226,227]
<i>Alstonia scholaris</i>	India, Thailand	α -glucosidase inhibitor	[227]
<i>Andrographis paniculata</i>	India (Ayurveda), Bangladesh, Nepal, Malaysia, Southeast Asia	antihyperglycemic	[81,107,116,228,229]
<i>Anthocephalus cadamba</i>	India (Ayurveda), Australia, China, Indonesia, Malaysia, Papua New Guinea, Philippines, Singapore, Vietnam	antidiabetic	[230]

<i>Aphanamixispolystachya</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[231]
<i>Argyreia nervosa</i>	India (Ayurveda)	Antidiabetic	[232]
<i>Asanadigana</i>	India (Ayurveda)	Antidiabetic	[233]
<i>Barringtonia acutangula</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[234]
<i>Basella rubra</i>	India	α -amylase inhibitor	[235]
<i>Begonia roxburghii</i>	India	antidiabetic	[49]
<i>Blepharismolluginifolia</i>	India	antidiabetic	[236]
<i>Boerhaviadiffusa</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[80]
<i>Boswellia ovalifoliolata</i>	India	antidiabetic	[237]
<i>Cajanus cajan</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[43]
<i>Callicarpa arborea</i>	India	antidiabetic	[49]
<i>Canna indica</i>		antidiabetic	[238]
<i>Casia fistula</i>	India (Ayurveda)	α -amylase inhibitor	[28]
<i>Cayratiatrifolia</i>	India	antidiabetic	[239]
<i>Ceiba pentandra</i>	India, Nigeria	α -amylase inhibition, hypoglycemic, antihyperglycemic	[240-242]
<i>Centella asiatica</i>	India (Ayurveda), Bangladesh, Malaysia, Laos, Southeast Asia	antidiabetic	[106,117,243-245]
<i>Centratherumanthelminticum</i>	India (Ayurveda)	hypoglycemic	[191,246]
<i>Chlorophytum borivilianum</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[247]
<i>Clitoriaternatea</i>	India (Ayurveda)	α -glucosidase, α -amylase inhibitor hypoglycemic	[164,248,249]
<i>Cocculus hirsutus</i>	India	α -amylase inhibitor	[235]
<i>Coldenia procumbens</i>	India	antidiabetic	[250]
<i>Commiphorawightii</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[80]
<i>Cosciniufenestratum</i>	India, Sri Lanka	antidiabetic	[251,252]
<i>Cuminum cyminum</i>	India	antidiabetic	[253]
<i>Cyamopsis tetragonoloba</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[254]
<i>Dendrocalamushamiltonii</i>	India (Ayurveda)	hypoglycemic	[63]

<i>Desmostachyabipinnata</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[255]
<i>Dillenia indica</i>	India	antidiabetic	[49]
<i>Diplazium esculentum</i>	India	antidiabetic	[49]
<i>Elaeocarpus ganitrus</i>	India (Ayurveda), Nepal	antidiabetic	[256]
<i>Emblica officinalis</i>	India (Ayurveda), Bangladesh	antidiabetic	[132,257,258]
<i>Enhydra fluctuans</i>	India	antidiabetic	[259]
<i>Feronia limonia</i>	India	antidiabetic	[260]
<i>Gloriosa superba</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[261]
<i>Glycosmis pentaphylla</i>	Siddha, India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[262]
<i>Gmelina arborea</i>	India, Sri Lanka	antidiabetic	[263,264]
<i>Gymnemasylvestre</i>	Ayurveda, Pakistan, Southeast Asia	hypoglycemic and antihyperglycemic	[117,265,266]
<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[267]
<i>Heritiera fomes</i>	India	antidiabetic	[268]
<i>Ichnocarpus frutescens</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[269]
<i>Imperata cylindrica</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[270]
<i>Lagenaria siceraria</i>	Mauritius, India (Ayurveda)	antihyperglycemic	[38,271,272]
<i>Lactuca gracilis</i>	India	antidiabetic	[49]
<i>Linum usitatissimum</i>	India (Ayurveda)	α -amylase inhibitor	[28]
<i>Meynalaxiflora</i>	India	antidiabetic	[273]
<i>Millingtonia hortensis</i>	India	antidiabetic	[49]
<i>Mukiamaderaspatana</i>	India (Ayurveda, Siddha)	antidiabetic	[274]
<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i>	India (Ayurveda), China (TCM), Southeast Asia	α -glucosidase, α -amylase inhibitor, hypoglycemic	[117,275-277]
<i>Nicotiana plumbaginifolia</i>	India	antidiabetic	[27]
<i>Nigella sativa</i>	Algeria, India (Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani), Pakistan, Morocco, Middle East, Mediterranean, North Africa	antidiabetic	[278-281]

<i>Nycantus arbor-tristis</i>	India (Ayurveda), Sri Lanka	hypoglycemic	[282]
<i>Odina wodier</i>	India	antidiabetic	[283]
<i>Oreocnide integrifolia</i>	India	antidiabetic	[284]
<i>Oroxylum indicum</i>	Bangladesh, India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[106,285]
<i>Pavonia zeylanica</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[227]
<i>Pergulariadaemia</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[286]
<i>Peucedanumpraeruptorum</i>	India (Ayurveda), China	antidiabetic	[287]
<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i>	Jordan, India (Ayurveda), Pakistan, Egypt	antidiabetic	[288-290]
<i>Pisonia grandis</i>	India	antidiabetic	[291]
<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i>	India	antidiabetic	[27]
<i>Polyalthia longifolia</i>	India	antidiabetic	[292]
<i>Pongamia pinnata</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antihyperglycemic	[293,294]
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i>	Trinidad and Tobago, India (Ayurveda), Algeria, Iran, China (TCM), Mexico	hypoglycemic	[295-298]
<i>Premna integrifolia</i>	India (Ayurveda)	hypoglycemic	[74]
<i>Psoralea corylifolia</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[299]
<i>Punica granatum</i>	India (Ayurveda, unani)	antidiabetic	[300-303]
<i>Roylea cinerea</i>	India	antidiabetic	[304]
<i>Rubia cordifolia</i>	India	antidiabetic	[305]
<i>Saccharum spontaneum</i>	India	antidiabetic	[49]
<i>Sesbeniaegyptiaca</i>	India (Ayurveda)	hypoglycemic	[63]
<i>Sphaeranthus indicus</i>	India	antidiabetic	[306]
<i>Stevia rebaudiana</i>	India, Paraguay, Brazil, south America	antidiabetic	[307,308]
<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	India (Ayurveda), Trinidad and Tobago, Africa	α amylase inhibitor	[37,309, 310]
<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antihyperglycemic	[311, 312]
<i>Thespesia populnea</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antihyperglycemic and hypoglycemic	[313]
<i>Tragiainvolucrata</i>	India (Ayurveda)	antidiabetic	[314]
<i>Viola odorata</i>	India	antidiabetic	[27]
<i>Wedeliatrilobata</i>	South America, China, Japan, India	antidiabetic	[315]

<i>Centhratherum</i>	India	Antidiabetic	[316]
<i>Casalpinia bonduc</i>	India	Antidiabetic	[316]

Marketed herbal Antidiabetic products:

Sr. NO.	Product	Manufacturer	Mechanism	Ref.
1	Sharang Dyab-Tea	Plant Med. Lab Pvt. Ltd	Stimulate insulin production	[317]
2	Herbal hill jambu	Isha Agro Developers	Reduce blood and urine sugar level	[318]
3	Stevia-33	Vitalize herbs	Maintain proper blood sugar level	[319]
4	Diab-FIT	Herbal FIT	Maintain proper blood sugar level	[320]
5	Madhumar capsule	Kangrd Hills Care and Cure Products	Control chronic diabetes mellitus	[321]
6	Daya Stone Powder	Jignesh and co.	Lowers the blood sugar level	[322]
7	Diabetone Tablet	Shelter Pharma Ltd.	Reduce blood sugar level by neutralize the level of pituitary secretion	[323]
8	Kumari-SAAR	Krishna herbal company	Maintain diabetic complication	[324]
9	Spenai	Shriji Herbal Products	Antidiabetic	[325]
10	Blue berry	A1-Hikma FZCO	Antidiabetic	[326]
11	Episulin	Varuna biocell Pvt.Ltd	Antidiabetic	[327]

CONCLUSION:

The global rise in diabetes prevalence has highlighted the need for innovative and holistic approaches to its management. While conventional antidiabetic medications are effective, their side effects often lead patients to seek alternative therapies. This review underscores the therapeutic potential of medicinal plants in diabetes management, with over 400 species demonstrating hypoglycemic properties. Many of these plants offer mechanisms that address key aspects of diabetes, such as enhancing insulin activity, inhibiting glucose absorption, and protecting pancreatic function. Importantly, traditional medicine systems like Ayurveda and Unani have long recognized the benefits of these plants, especially in rural populations that rely heavily on herbal remedies. As research into these botanical treatments continues, there is significant promise in integrating them with conventional

medical approaches to provide a more comprehensive, side-effect-free management of diabetes. However, more clinical studies are needed to validate their efficacy and safety. The future of diabetes treatment may well lie in the synergy between modern pharmacology and traditional plant-based medicine

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